

The Challenges of the Human Resources Professionals in the Face of Precariousness Work in Brazil

Os Desafios dos Profissionais de Recursos Humanos diante da Precarização do Trabalho no Brasil
Los Desafios de los Profesionales de Recursos Humanos ante la precariedad del Trabajo en Brasil

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Abstract:

Conceived as a fundamental human right and established in both international and Brazilian law, decent work seeks to ensure the dignity of each person, by safeguarding their health and safety, while also providing fair remuneration, to promote social equity and reduce poverty. In this context, this essay addresses the challenges faced by Human Resources (HR) professionals, who play a strategic role within organizations, especially given the constant changes in legislation and the precariousness growing of work in Brazil, due to labor market reorganization and the resulting fragility of labor relations. The State's push for more flexible legislation has led to more fragile employment relationships and new types of contracts, such as autonomous, temporary, intermittent work, subcontracting (outsourcing and fourth-party contracting), "pejotização" (contracting individuals as legal entities), and "uberization" or platform-mediated work. Furthermore, the Labor Reform has intensified this trend, removing rights and reducing social protections. Therefore, HR managers are responsible for ensuring compliance with current regulations and maintaining a proper work environment, even in this challenging scenario.

Keywords: *Modernity; Work; Fundamental Right; Precariousness.*

Resumo:

Concebido como um direito humano fundamental, previsto em normas de direito internacional e de direito brasileiro, o trabalho decente procura garantir a dignidade de cada indivíduo, mediante a proteção de sua saúde e segurança, assim como uma justa remuneração, visando à promoção de equidade social e à diminuição da pobreza. Nessa conjuntura, essa pesquisa aborda os desafios enfrentados pelos profissionais de Recursos Humanos (RH), que possuem papel estratégico nas organizações, diante da constante alteração das leis e da crescente precarização do trabalho no Brasil, decorrente da reorganização no mercado de trabalho e da consequente fragilidade das relações trabalhistas. A flexibilização da legislação promovida pelo Estado resultou em vínculos empregatícios mais delicados e em novas modalidades de contrato, como o trabalho autônomo, o temporário, o intermitente, a subcontratação (terceirização e quarteirização), a "pejotização" e a "uberização" ou trabalho mediado por plataforma. Além disso, a Reforma Trabalhista intensificou essa tendência, retirando direitos e reduzindo a proteção social. Desse

modo, cabe aos gestores de RH, a responsabilidade de cumprir as normas vigentes e gerenciar um ambiente de trabalho adequado, mesmo diante desse cenário.

Palavras-chave: Modernidade; Trabalho; Direito Fundamental; Precarização.

Resumen:

Concebido como un derecho humano fundamental, previsto en normas de derecho internacional y de derecho brasileño, el trabajo decente busca garantizar la dignidad de cada individuo mediante la protección de su salud y seguridad, así como una remuneración justa, con el fin de promover la equidad social y reducir la pobreza. En este contexto, esta investigación aborda los desafíos que enfrentan los profesionales de Recursos Humanos (RRHH), quienes tienen un papel estratégico en las organizaciones, ante la constante modificación de las leyes y la creciente precarización del trabajo en Brasil, derivada de la reorganización del mercado laboral y la consecuente fragilidad de las relaciones laborales. La flexibilización de la legislación promovida por el Estado ha resultado en vínculos laborales más frágiles y en nuevas modalidades de contrato, como el trabajo autónomo, temporal, intermitente, la subcontratación (tercerización y cuarteirización), la “pejotización” y la “uberización” o trabajo mediado por plataforma. Además, la Reforma Laboral intensificó esta tendencia, recortando derechos y reduciendo la protección social. De este modo, corresponde a los gestores de RRHH la responsabilidad de cumplir con las normas vigentes y gestionar un ambiente laboral adecuado, incluso ante este escenario.

Palabras clave: Modernidad; Trabajo; Derecho Fundamental; Precarización.

1. INTRODUCTION

It must be borne in mind that, in a highly globalized world under a capitalist political-economic system, for a company to consolidate and prosper in an extremely "aggressive" market, it must guarantee ever-increasing profits with ever-decreasing investments and resource use.

This heightened market demand leads to the creation and use of various strategies aimed at competitiveness and, consequently, at the survival of business establishments, which seek to maximize their profits and thus annihilate the competition.

In the mid-1970s and 1980s, the implementation of new models of work corporations and management, and the insertion of technological innovations (based on microelectronics) into the production process of organizations, generated a direct impact on the world of work, replacing manual labor with machinery (Vieira, 2014), hence promoting the precariousness of working conditions and the lives of workers (Melges et al., 2022), such as the growth of structural unemployment, the increase in informality among salaried workers, the widening of social inequality, and the destruction of social safety nets (Faria; Kremer, 2004).

At that time, a greater flexibility in labor legislation sponsored by the State began, characterized by allowing new forms of work enterprise and the weakening of employment relationships, giving rise to new patterns of employee hiring, such as part-time work, self-employment, temporary work, and outsourcing, among others, which were incorporated over time. (Faria; Kremer, 2004).

The major problem in this context, however, is the disregard for human rights, social rights, labor law, and workers' health and safety standards, since there is no symmetry between the power of employers (who own the means of production) and employees (who are often underprivileged), who are frequently subjected to precarious working conditions and uncertainty about the future owing to the need for subsistence.

Given this scenario, the objective of this article is to discuss the challenges faced by Human Resources professionals amid weakening worker protection regulations and the importance of reconciling business competitiveness with respect for decent and safe work.

This paper discusses the importance of work, the right to (decent) work, and the reduction of legal protections for labor, especially in light of the 2017 labor reform, popularly known in legal circles as the "labor deformation," as many workers' rights were suppressed under the guise of modernizing legislation and allowing free negotiation between employers and union representatives, or the workers themselves, to increase the number of formal job opportunities. (Kalil, 2016).

Given the above, the social relevance of deepening studies on this topic is justified, even more so when considering the polarized political moment in which Brazil is immersed, where neoliberal ideals and the reduction of the State's presence in the economy (Minimal State) are emerging, becoming established and spreading, generating attacks on human and social rights, making them, each day, more flexible and, consequently, fragile. (Vieira, 2014).

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Work, the Right to Work and Decent Work

The concept of work, as developed throughout history, has undergone several modifications owing to social evolution and advances in production relations. Similarly, regulations governing labor rights have also evolved.

Nowadays, work can be defined as a "human activity, material or intellectual, whereby scarce goods and services are produced, necessary for the reproduction of individual and collective life." (Vargas, 2024, p. 4, our translation).

In this context, the right to work is considered an essential human right, whose objective is to ensure citizenship and the dignity of individuals, providing the opportunity to engage in decent professional activity, personal fulfillment, a "fair" remuneration that allows for the enjoyment of a good life (Alvarenga, 2008), and consequently, means of support for oneself and family members (dependents). (Sousa, 2018).

By enabling all people, without any distinction, regardless of gender, age, race, creed, sexual orientation, or disability, to have access to decent jobs, with adequate working conditions, appropriate remuneration, and respect for current regulations, the construction of a less unjust and more equitable society is guaranteed, mitigating social inequalities and the devastating effects of poverty. (Sousa, 2018; Souza et al., 2018).

The Right to Work is enshrined in various legal systems, both supranational, international and national, such as, for example, the Conventions of the International Labour Organization - ILO ratified by Brazil (and other sovereign states), the Universal Declaration of Human Rights - UDHR, of 1948; the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights - ICESCR, of 1966; and the MERCOSUR Socio-Labor Declaration of 2015. Regarding Brazilian labor law, the essential guidelines are found in the Brazilian Federal Constitution of 1988, the Consolidation of Labor Laws of 1943, and in sub-constitutional laws.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights - UDHR, in the words of Teixeira (2018, p. 67, our translation), is pointed out as:

A landmark in the history of human rights, as it was drafted by representatives of different legal backgrounds and cultures from the most diverse regions of the world, making it clear that it is possible to reach a point of convergence for establishing the rights and obligations of States, even in the face of their most varied particularities. It is also a symbol for establishing, for the first time, a standard guideline to be achieved by all peoples and nations: the universal protection of human rights. The Declaration brought significant innovations, especially regarding the sole requirement for entitlement to the rights guaranteed therein: the status of being a person.

In summary, the UDHR came to precisely define the list of "human rights and fundamental freedoms" (PIOVESAN, 2016, p. 216), among which we can enumerate: decent and dignified work, free choice of employment, protection against unemployment, and fair remuneration that provides human beings with an existence compatible with human dignity. This international law also provides for the right to rest,

reasonable limits on working hours (daily and weekly), leisure, and paid holidays. (UNITED NATIONS, 1948).

Complementing the provisions of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) recognizes the importance of every person having the opportunity to earn a living using freely chosen work, under just and favorable working conditions, in a safe and hygienic environment, with adequate remuneration. It adds, in addition to the need for periodic rest and vacations, the need to delimit working hours and to remunerate holidays. (ORGANIZATION OF AMERICAN STATES, 1966).

In turn, the MERCOSUR [\[1\]](#)Socio-Labor Declaration ensures that all workers in the Member States of the Southern Common Market have access to quality jobs under adequate conditions, aiming to promote their well-being. Its purpose is to reconcile economic development processes with social justice, consequently improving the living conditions of its inhabitants.

In fact, the labor rights outlined in the MERCOSUR Socio-Labor Declaration were derived from other international treaties to which the Member States had already committed themselves, reinforcing the importance of decent work in citizens' lives and of respect for labor law standards.

As stated by Teixeira (2018, pp. 48-49, our translation),

Socio-Labor Declaration mandates the production of studies and lists the objectives to be achieved by the Member States. Through it, members commit to promoting and ensuring decent work; the development of sustainable enterprises; effective equality of rights without any type of distinction or exclusion; elimination of forced or compulsory labor; prevention and eradication of child labor and protection of adolescent workers; employers' rights; limitation of working hours; the right to rest, vacations and holidays; the right to enjoy paid and unpaid leave; guaranteeing remuneration capable of meeting the needs of the worker and their family by means of the establishment of a minimum wage policy; protection against dismissal; freedom of association; promotion of collective bargaining; guaranteeing the right to strike; promotion and development of preventive procedures and self-resolution of conflicts; promotion of social dialogue by the implementation of means of consultation with representatives of governments, employers and workers; centrality and promotion of employment.; protection for the unemployed; vocational training for employed and unemployed workers; Implementation of a national occupational health and safety system that ensures the continuous improvement of working conditions and the work environment; establishment and maintenance of labor inspection services; and, last but not least, the promotion of social security, such as guaranteeing a minimum income for all inhabitants in the face of adverse social contingencies.

Regarding national legislation, the Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil, popularly known as the "Citizen Constitution" for its focus on social rights, has brought significant advances in labor rights. Many guarantees already enshrined in the Consolidation of Labor Laws (CLT) have gained constitutional status (Superior Labor

Court, 2018); that is, they have attained the highest position in the hierarchy of laws of a country. (Neves, 2015).

Article 6 of the Constitution, as amended by Constitutional Amendment No. 90 of 2015, provides: “The following are social rights: education, health, food, work, housing, transportation, leisure, security, social security, protection of motherhood and childhood, and assistance to the destitute, as provided for in this Constitution.” (Brazil, 1988, our translation), (emphasis added).

In turn, Article 7 of the Constitution lists all the rights of urban and rural workers who perform their duties in Brazilian territory:

Article 7. The following are rights of urban and rural workers, in addition to others aimed at improving their social condition:

I - employment relationship protected against arbitrary dismissal or dismissal without just cause, under the terms of a supplementary law, which will provide for compensatory indemnification, among other rights;

II - unemployment insurance, in case of involuntary unemployment;

III - severance pay guarantee fund;

IV - minimum wage;

(...)

XXXIII - prohibition of night work, dangerous or unhealthy work for minors under eighteen years of age and any work for minors under sixteen years of age, except as an apprentice, starting at fourteen years of age;

XXXIV - Equality of rights between workers with permanent employment contracts and casual workers.

Sole paragraph. Domestic workers are guaranteed the rights provided for in items IV, VI, VII, VIII, X, XIII, XV, XVI, XVII, XVIII, XIX, XXI, XXII, XXIV, XXVI, XXX, XXXI and XXXIII and, subject to the conditions established by law and observing the simplification of compliance with the principal and accessory tax obligations arising from the employment relationship and its peculiarities, those provided for in items I, II, III, IX, XII, XXV and XXVIII, as well as their integration into social security. (Brazil, 1988). (emphasis added).

Given all this labor law framework that protects work, it can be stated that decent work is that which respects these norms, ensuring a minimum of rights and dignity for the worker, including protection against social risks, their health and safety; adequate remuneration under fair conditions, allowing freedom of association and prohibiting child labor and labor in conditions analogous to slavery. (Brito Filho, 2016; Theodoro Júnior, Gomes, 2017).

2.2 Flexibility and Precariousness of Work

In Brazil and several other Latin American countries, the 1980s are known as the "lost decade" because of the devastating economic crisis that plagued the period. At the time, external debt skyrocketed, severely shaking the country's economy and leading to inflation and its consequences: marked instability, currency devaluation, loss of purchasing power, and unemployment, among others, in the face of low growth and market uncertainties. (Silva, 2016).

Under such conditions, Castro (2001) argues that structural changes occurred in world capitalism, with companies undergoing major reorganization, the spread of new management practices, and the adoption of new production techniques aimed at modernization and cost reduction to gain a competitive advantage.

This new production pattern is characterized primarily by the introduction and intensification of technological innovations (Pires, 2000), which have replaced a large portion of human labor, increasing unemployment and causing economic difficulties and social suffering (Gerbaudo, 2017 apud Andrade, 2019).

Over at the turn of the 1990s, the economic situation led to a series of structural reforms, privatizations (Quiñones, 2011) and austerity policies, characterized mainly by profound effects on people: by cuts in public spending, implying a reduction in investments in health, education, social assistance and compromising the implementation of public policies. (Gerbaudo, 2017 apud Andrade, 2019).

As stated by Alves (2009, p. 190, our translation),

The neoliberal reforms implemented since the Collor administration and the macroeconomic scenario (recession or low economic growth in a context of intense industrial restructuring, high interest rates, and trade liberalization with intensified inter-capitalist competition) contributed to a scenario of labor market degradation with a high rate of total unemployment in metropolitan areas and deterioration of wage contracts result from the expansion of informalization and outsourcing in large companies, aimed at reducing costs.

These events have generated consequences that are still felt in Brazil today: impacts on jobs, increasingly degraded by imposed flexibility; effects on the population's standard of living; widening social inequality; and high levels of poverty.

Vieira explains (2014, p. 12, our translation):

Flexibility arises from several complex factors we studied above, namely: political (neoliberalism), economic (global crisis), transformations in the work process, and technological innovations (automation, robotics, information technology, communication networks, among others).

In other words, the economic market demands a flexibilization/weakening of traditional, legally regulated labor relations because it needs norms that are easily adaptable to the market situation and the volatile, fluctuating economic climate. (Vieira, 2014).

Concerning the scope of Labor Law, Vieira (2014, p. 13, our translation) clarifies that:

(...) Flexibility can be defined as the reduction, elimination, easing, loosening, or adaptation of classic labor protections. It aims to

increase flexibility for employers and employees amid economic difficulties caused by the global crisis, while addressing the perception that labor legislation's protective nature impedes economic growth.

In this sense, capitalism demands the constant transformation of traditional employment relationships, with the emergence of new forms of work relationships and, in some cases, the absence of relationships, an attribute of informal work (Faria; Kremer, 2004) and the new forms of work that have emerged over the last few decades. "The aim of flexibility is the total and definitive breaking of the employment relationship, that is, everything for profit, including the trivialization of the fundamental rights of the working human being." (Vieira, 2014, p. 2, our translation).

2.3 Micro-injuries to Workers' Rights and Social Dumping

Article 3 of the Consolidation of Labor Laws clarifies that "an employee is considered to be any individual who provides non-occasional services to an employer, under the employer's direction and for a salary." (Brazil, 1943, our translation). Article 12, IA of the Organic Law of Social Security adds that these functions can be performed in urban or rural areas. (Brazil, 1991).

From this definition, it follows that there are five requirements for a person to be considered an employee: a) being a natural person; b) providing services of a non-occasional nature; c) economic dependence; d) receiving a salary; and e) personal provision of services. (Martins, 2024).

In turn, an employer can be a natural person who runs a business and carries out some activity and, for that purpose, hires employees (Martins, 2024) or a company (legal entity) that "assumes the risks of the economic activity, hires, pays wages to and directs the personal provision of services." (Brazil, 1943, our translation).

In the current context in which Brazil is situated (a capitalist and globalized world, with high competition and filled with elements of flexible labor relations resulting from neoliberalism), nevertheless, some people and organizations use subterfuge or cunning practices in their management to gain a competitive edge over other companies, regardless of whether these mechanisms are illegal and harmful to workers. It should also be noted that many of these behaviors constitute an actual attack on the dignity of the employee as a human being and can affect their health, safety, and quality of life.

Among these practices, we can mention microinjuries and social dumping.

A microlesion, as claimed by Kolowski and Sampaio (2018, pp. 35-36), is characterized by the repetition of intentional harmful acts "that have apparent irrelevance from an individual point of view, but which are significantly advantageous from an economic point of view when considered in their entirety."

In Labor Law, Kolowski and Sampaio (2018, p. 36, our translation) state that:

(...) Micro-injuries are small frauds applied discreetly that are often mistaken for "errors" in counting or calculating the payment of certain labor benefits or even in the legal classification of certain

situations, which are repeated over successive unpaid or partially paid installments while the employment contract.

They cite as examples the lack of employee registration, underpayment (of weekly rest periods, overtime, bonuses, related benefits, commissions or tips), reduction of breaks without corresponding salary payment, disregard of certain items as a basis for calculating FGTS (Brazilian severance pay fund), withholding of amounts for INSS (Brazilian social security) payment without due collection, non-compliance with collective bargaining agreements or collective work agreements, poor working conditions, excessive pressure to meet targets, etc. (Kolowski; Sampaio, 2018).

In accordance with the General Report of the Labor Courts (2024, p. 6, our translation), “in the year 2023, 3,539,091 cases were judged in the Labor Courts, 11.5% more than in 2022.”

The most recurring issues in labor lawsuits, as stated by statistics compiled by the Superior Labor Court (2024), are: severance pay, hazard pay, 40% FGTS fine, fine under article 477 of the CLT, compensation for moral damages, overtime, FGTS, fine under article 467 of the CLT, prior notice, meal break, constructive dismissal, working hours, proportional vacation pay, proportional 13th salary, overtime pay, recognition of employment relationship, attorney's fees in Labor Court, outstanding wages, danger pay, and night shift differential.

As this list shows, a large share of labor lawsuits is filed thanks to employers' practice of micro-injuries, which they use to increase their profits from surplus value. Nonetheless, this does not demonstrate ignorance of the law; it denotes systematic infringing behavior intended to obtain economic advantage at the expense of amounts owed to employees. (Kolowski; Sampaio, 2018).

This practice is also called social dumping, which, in short, is a recurring issue in developing peripheral countries, in which companies, especially those focused on the global market, aim to reduce the costs of their products by using cheaper and more precarious labor, disregarding basic labor and social security rights, and also engaging in unfair competition, to gain new market share in goods and products, eliminating their competitors (Santos, 2015).

In short, social dumping is a form of micro-injury because it is a practice in which labor rights are repeatedly and deliberately evaded to obtain profits and economic advantages over other market participants, allowing for increased earnings without concern for the consequences suffered by workers, who in many cases are harmed in their most basic social and fundamental rights, such as health and safety at work (Souto Maior; Moreira; Severo, 2014; Kolowski; Sampaio, 2018; Costa; Merheb, 2019).

2.4 Self-Employment

Self-employment or cooperative work represents an increasingly common form of work institution in the Brazilian market, following an international trend of labor flexibilization. On a large scale, they increase informality and precariousness in the world of work (Georges and Silva, 2007), reflecting changes driven by technological progress and economic problems, such as unemployment (Amorim, 2023).

Article 12, IV-A and B of the Organic Law of Social Security establishes that a self-employed worker is one who "provides services of an urban or rural nature, on an occasional basis, to one or more companies, without an employment relationship" or "a natural person who carries out, on their own account, an economic activity of an urban nature, for profit or not." (Brazil, 1991).

In other words, a self-employed worker is a natural person who, on their own account, provides their services, without any legal subordination, to one or more natural or legal persons. Because there is no subordination, the economic risk of this activity lies with the self-employed worker, and not with the service recipient. (Losso; Losso, 2014).

Examples of self-employed workers include contractors, sales representatives, and freelance professionals. (Santos, 2015).

The Labor Reform instituted by Federal Law No. 13.467/2017 created the figure of the "exclusively self-employed" worker. The new article 442-B (our translation) of the CLT stipulates: "the hiring of a self-employed worker, provided that all legal formalities are fulfilled, with or without exclusivity, continuously or not, excludes the status of employee as provided for in article 3 of this Consolidation."

The hiring of self-employed workers to provide exclusive services to a company is quite common, even before this legal change. In fact, it's important to remember that recognition of an employment relationship is one of the most recurring issues in labor lawsuits, as indicated by data from the Superior Labor Court (2024).

Nevertheless, the State's creation of this new legal figure represents an attempt to strengthen the protection of companies that hire only self-employed workers who continuously provide services to the same institution, since it circumvents the obligation to grant employment contracts to workers. (Leal, 2019).

Some criticize the innovation, suggesting that it facilitates the practice of "pejotização," a phenomenon in which an employee is distorted into a service provider via a legal entity, lacking the rights and guarantees typical of a salaried worker, to reduce the contracting company's financial responsibilities.

On the other hand, proponents of the legislative change argue that it does not legalize the use of independent contractors but instead provides legal security to those who choose to hire self-employed workers exclusively. However, not a requirement for an employment relationship was considered an element in determining whether such a relationship existed (Leal, 2019, p. 82).

This normative provision restricted the concept of employee, excluding a large portion of the working class from the guarantees of labor law, including those related to health and safety at work, by enabling any worker to be self-employed, regardless of their dedication and attendance (Galvão et al., 2017).

2.5 Temporary Work

Temporary work is one of the oldest forms of precarious employment, after the systematization of labor rights in a single document - the CLT, in 1943, during the Getúlio Vargas government. (Alves, 2022).

Law No. 6,019/1974 [2], as amended by Law No. 13,429/2017, provides that:

Article 2. Temporary work is performed by a natural person hired by a temporary employment agency, which then makes that person available to a client company to meet the need for temporary replacement of permanent staff or to meet additional service demands. (Brazil, 1974).

"Demand for services is considered supplementary when it arises from unpredictable factors or, when resulting from predictable factors, is intermittent, periodic, or seasonal in nature." (§ 2, art. 2 of Law No. 6.019/1974).

In this way, when hired, the worker is aware that their employment contract has a start and end date, characterizing a fixed-term service provision to meet the company's temporary need, unlike indefinite-term employment contracts (Nakahashi, 2023).

It should be noted that Decree No. 10,060/2019, which currently regulates this type of work, has brought about some changes that are detrimental to workers, including cutting previously existing rights (Aranha, 2020), with the justification of modernizing legislation, bringing greater legal security to employers, and creating new jobs to improve the Brazilian economy (Veiga, 2019).

Among the fundamental changes, the following can be mentioned: the possibility of the temporary employment contract covering the development of core activities to be performed at the client company and not only the development of support activities, as was the case in the 1974 legislation (Article 9, § 3 of Law No. 6.019/1974); the clarification that, regardless of the client company's sector, there is no employment relationship between it and the workers hired by temporary employment agencies (Article 10 of Law No. 6.019/1974); the duration of the temporary employment contract, which was 3 months, became a maximum term of up to 180 days, with the possibility of being extended for up to 90 days (Article 10, §§ 1 and 2 of Law No. 6.019/1974). (Aranha, 2020; Nakahashi, 2023).

Finally, it is worth noting that temporary work is considered the "best business alternative for hiring workers in an atypical way, due to its flexibility and rapid recruitment of the workforce" (Barros, 2019, our translation), as well as for the convenience and simplicity of replacing labor.

2.6 Intermittent Work

Among the many novelties introduced into the Consolidation of Labor Laws by Law No. 13,467/2017, popularly known as the "labor reform," the creation of a new type of employment contract in Brazilian labor law stands out: the intermittent employment contract, provided for in § 3 of art. 443 and regulated in the arts. 452-A to 452-H. (Brazil, 1943).

This type of contract establishes an employment relationship with variable working hours and salary, as maintained by the employer's needs and demands. Legislators justify

the intermittent contract proposal as an alternative to informal work, aiming to reduce the country's unemployment rate. (D'Amorim, 2018).

The definition of an intermittent work contract is found in paragraph 3 of article 443 of the CLT (Consolidation of Labor Laws), which states:

Article 443. The individual employment contract may be agreed upon tacitly or expressly, verbally or in writing, for a fixed or indefinite term, or for intermittent work.

(...)

§ 3. An intermittent employment contract is considered to be one in which the provision of services, under subordination, is not continuous, occurring with alternating periods of service and inactivity, determined in hours, days or months, regardless of the type of activity of the employee and the employer, except for aeronauts, who are governed by their own legislation. (Brazil, 1943). (emphasis added).

Intermittent work, then, can be described as work in which the provision of services is discontinuous or interrupted, although subordination exists.

D'Amorim (2018, p. 29, our translation) clarifies that:

An intermittent work contract is an open-ended contract without a defined work schedule. In this type of contract, periods of service may alternate with periods of inactivity that can last hours, days, or months, regardless of the kind of activity performed by the employee or the employer.

Consequently, it can be stated that in this type of work relationship, an employment bond is established. Nonetheless, the employee's remuneration will be variable, according to the time that he or she actually puts their labor up for sale and is called upon to work. (Barreto, 2017).

Furthermore, intermittent work, despite being part of an open-ended contractual relationship, constitutes a new form of precarious work because the worker does not have a fixed schedule and, consequently, their earnings are proportional to the number of hours actually worked. (Accarini et al., 2018 Apud Barros, 2019).

D'Amorim summarizes (2018, p. 29, our translation):

The intermittent work contract assumes that the worker is called upon by the employer as needed and is paid for the hours actually worked. For this reason, in this type of contract, the worker is available to the employer, awaiting a call to work. If the call does not occur, they will not be paid for the time they were available. This implies that there is no guaranteed minimum remuneration for the worker.

This type of employment contract disregards workers' basic need for a minimum income for survival and to honor their commitments, thereby violating Brazilian constitutional principles. (Barros, 2019).

2.7 Outsourcing and Subcontracting

Outsourcing and sub-outsourcing in the workplace have changed the productive and service-provision structure in Brazil, making it “leaner” in recent decades and weakening employment relationships through the flexibilization of labor law regulations (Fontoura, 2017).

It emerged as a guise for a “modern management technique” (Marcelino; Cavalcante, 2012), advocating the idea that companies should focus on their “core activities” and delegate ancillary tasks and processes (“support activities”), such as cleaning, security, surveillance, maintenance, and catering, to other specialized companies (Balbino; Silva, 2016).

Similarly, Martinez (2014, p. 262) conceptualizes outsourcing as “a technique for organizing the production process whereby a company, aiming to concentrate efforts on its core activity, contracts another company, understood as peripheral, to provide support in merely instrumental services.” Nevertheless, in practice, outsourcing and sub-outsourcing are used in Brazil to reduce payroll costs (Frez; Mello, 2016), thus increasing organizations' profits and assisting in the resumption of the country's economic growth (Costa; Merheb, 2019).

Marcelino and Cavalcante (2012) and Frez and Mello (2016) state that this transformation in the labor market has led to a general decline in the working and employment conditions of subcontracted categories, increasing the trend towards precarious working conditions, evidenced by wage and rights losses, increased working hours, and risks to workers' health and safety.

Law No. 6,019/1974, as amended by Law No. 13,429/2017 and worded as amended by Law No. 13,467/2017, declares that:

Article 4-A. The provision of services to third parties is considered the transfer by the contracting party of the execution of any of its activities, including its principal activity, to a private legal entity with economic capacity to perform them.

§ 1 The service provider company hires, remunerates, and directs the work performed by its employees [3], or subcontracts other companies [4] to perform these services. (Brazil, 1974). (emphasis added).

The terms outsourcing and sub-outsourcing are, in short, synonyms for subcontracting. Nevertheless, regarding the origin of these institutions, both can be considered “a natural unfolding of the division of labor in capitalism” (Marcelino and Cavalcante, 2012, p. 337).

2.8 “Pejotização” and “Uberização” or Platform-Based Work

An employment relationship ensures workers' protection under Labor Law, as provided for in both the Consolidation of Labor Laws and the Federal Constitution of Brazil, guaranteeing them a set of social rights that enable their daily subsistence and provide additional support beyond work activities. (Barbosa; Orbem, 2015).

Despite this, many workers, out of necessity for survival, resort to fraudulent practices, including "pejotização" (contracting via a company that uses independent contractors to avoid labor laws) and "uberização" (or platform-based work), in the face of high unemployment rates.

Krein's teachings (2018, p. 104), "pejotização" refers to:

(...) a process of masking and legally eliminating employment relationships, consolidating itself by transforming employees into service providers, legally recognized as a legal entity. It is, whence, about eliminating the employment relationship to recognize and establish working relationships with the now self-employed worker, who is deprived of the rights, protections, and guarantees associated with salaried employment.

Accordingly, the worker, a natural person, in the words of Barbosa, Orbem (2015, p. 2, our translation):

(...) To be hired or to maintain a job at a particular company, it is necessary to establish a legal entity, such as a sole proprietorship or a business corporation. In this way, there will be an inter-company relationship, regulated by Civil Law, in which the worker will provide services to the contracting company under a service agreement formalized between the contracting company and the worker's legal entity, without any labor rights applying.

In other words, in the case of "pejotização" (a term referring to the practice of forcing employees to become independent contractors), a service provision contract is used to disguise an employment relationship, excluding workers' protections and leading to a new form of precarious employment. The contracting parties have few obligations regarding social security contributions and labor rights. (Costa, 2021).

Concerning "uberization" or platform work, a new framework for workers is emerging, in which they assume responsibility in the production chain, mediated by an application that connects clients to service providers. (Franco; Ferraz, 2019).

Franco and Ferraz (2019, p. 2, our translation) add that these people act as:

(...) without any employment relationship, working as self-employed professionals and assuming various risks to offer the service, owning almost all the means of production necessary to carry out the activity and being fully responsible for them. Considering that the Brazilian Labor Law (...), this worker is, in addition to being compelled to invest in the instruments of work, unprotected in this work relationship.

In short, these forms of work lead to "precariousness, exploitation and disarticulation of formal workers, based on the fallacy of becoming one's own boss, under the illusory form of entrepreneurship" (Costa, 2021, p. 10), encouraging working hours longer than those permitted by Brazilian law and eliminating existing guarantees and protections (Krein, 2018).

It is important to emphasize that the Brazilian State provides a specific incentive to these types of work, facilitating and simplifying the process of obtaining registration as a micro-entrepreneur (MEI), to promote the legalization of companies and businesses, as can be

seen in Article 4, § 1, of Complementary Law 128/2008, and in Article 1 of Complementary Law 123/2006, which explicitly provides "differentiated treatment (...) to micro-enterprises and small businesses."

2.9 The Labor Reform

Brazil has been experiencing substantial changes in labor legislation since the Fernando Henrique Cardoso administration in the 1990s, in response to intense pressure from capital to make social and economic relations more flexible (Fonseca; Melo Filho, 2023).

Nonetheless, Krein (2018, p. 77, our translation) points out that:

The year 2017 will possibly be known as the year in which the Federal Government and the Brazilian Congress dealt a severe blow to the poorest by approving the dismantling of social and labor rights won by the Brazilian people over the last hundred years.

Enacted by way of the Law No. 13,467/2017, the labor reform brought significant changes to employment conditions in Brazil, revising more than 100 provisions of the Consolidation of Labor Laws (CLT) (Pantaleão, n.d.), which were considered obsolete.

The vital objectives of the labor reform, given the ultraliberal agenda in which Brazil is involved, included the resumption of economic growth and the generation of employment and income (Krein; Colombi, 2019), by means of the modernization and debureaucratization of labor rules and the adaptation of legislation to new labor relations, ensuring greater legal security for companies. (National Confederation of Industry, 2017).

Nonetheless, one cannot ignore the principal consequences of this reform, which dismantled several workers' rights, extinguishing and making them more flexible. Examples include legal changes that introduced new forms of employment, flexible working hours and remuneration; the weakening of public institutions and union company; and the individualization of risks (Krein, 2018), reducing social protection for salaried workers and subjecting them to a situation of greater risk and vulnerability (Galvão, 2018).

It is worth noting that, despite all the "promises" that justified the labor reform, the Brazilian reality has not undergone significant changes, with the Brazilian labor market continuing to exhibit unemployment, informality, and increasing underutilization of the workforce.

After the reform, considering the total number of employees with formal contracts, incomes fell from the first month the new law came into effect; workers' wages worsened over time; profits grew, but the investment rate in Brazil remained close to the lowest levels in its history, reaching its lowest level in the last 50 years in the first quarter of 2019; Brazil ceased to be one of the priority countries for foreign investment; total unemployment increased; hidden unemployment (underemployment) grew; (...) informal and illegal employment grew more than formal employment. (Fonseca; Melo Filho, 2023, p. 25).

In short, one can deduce that the labor reform served only to make labor law regulations more flexible and to erode workers' rights, thereby increasing job insecurity under the pretext of modernization.

2.10 The Challenges Faced by Human Resources Professionals Regarding Job Insecurity

Human Resources professionals have several functions within a business, including: recruitment and selection of personnel; management of interpersonal relationships; management of organizational climate; career management; performance management; strategic compensation; financial management; management of personnel routines; and corporate communication. (Bilhim, 2009; Chiavenato, 2014; Pires, 2018).

In this context, the Human Resources sector plays a fundamental role in the organizational structure of any institution, whether public or private. This is even more true in the current scenario, where the world of work is constantly transforming due to the reorganization of the means of production.

Alongside the process of productive restructuring, there is an ongoing process of precarious employment relationships, owing to the flexibilization of labor legislation sponsored by the State. (Faria; Kremer, 2004).

Legal changes and the precariousness of work significantly impact professionals in the Human Resources sector, presenting numerous challenges.

First, they must be aware of changes brought about by legislation to avoid fines, penalties, or labor lawsuits. (Time Pontotel, 2024).

It is essential to have advanced knowledge of Labor Law, as personnel legislation is constantly evolving. (Fortes Tecnologia, 2023).

Furthermore, it is necessary to be aware of new forms of personnel hiring: freelance work, temporary work, intermittent work, subcontracting (outsourcing and fourth-party outsourcing), in order to manage the workforce.

In summary, HR professionals hold a strategic position in people management, ensuring a positive work environment for everyone, regardless of employment contract type, thus achieving greater operational efficiency.

3. METHOD

This section of the academic article presents the methodological aspects used in this research, which supported the achievement of the proposed objectives.

The work carried out is qualitative and exploratory, offering critical reflections on the topic presented.

This study was based on bibliographic research. In line with the proposed objectives, secondary research sources were used, including a literature review

encompassing books, monographs, scientific articles, websites, magazines, and newspapers, all related to the project's theme.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Reflecting on the entire legal framework that governs the relationship between the Brazilian State and its citizens, it can be affirmed that the right to work is enshrined in international and national regulations, including the Conventions of the International Labour Organization (ILO) ratified by Brazil and other countries, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), and the MERCOSUR Socio-Labor Declaration, all incorporated into the Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil, known as the "Citizen Constitution". Within the scope of Brazilian labor law, the crucial guidelines are found in the Constitution and the Consolidation of Labor Laws (CLT). (emphasis added).

The common elements among all these norms consist of the recognition of dignified and decent work as a fundamental human right and the importance of guaranteeing the dignity of the worker by means of the provision of adequate and favorable working conditions, in a safe and hygienic environment, with fair remuneration that provides for their livelihood and quality of life.

Despite this, in the mid-1980s, amid a severe economic crisis, a process of structural change began in global capitalism, reflected in the reorganization of companies and the implementation of new management practices and production techniques aimed at modernizing corporations and reducing costs to achieve greater competitiveness.

In this context, many people lost their jobs thanks to the increased use of machines and technology. Furthermore, this situation led to the onset of a process of precariousness and weakening of labor relations, initially marked by micro-violations of labor rights and social dumping, and later by legislative changes that negatively impacted the population's standard of living.

Wherefore, over the last few decades, new forms of employment contracts have emerged, more flexible and easily adaptable to market interests, which demonize" labor rights as being responsible for the low profitability of corporations and the low growth of the country's economy. It is also worth noting that these were the reasons for the 2017 labor reform.

In light of this, the importance of Human Resources professionals in managing all these increasingly frequent changes becomes clear. And therein lies the challenge: staying up to date to properly guide both employers and employees.

5. CONCLUSION

Considering all the above, it can be stated that the right to decent work is a fundamental and vital right of human beings, enshrined in the national legal system (the Federal Constitution and the Consolidation of Labor Laws) and in foreign law (International Conventions and Pacts ratified by Brazil).

Labor law, therefore, serves as a tool to balance the relationship between the contracting party (worker) and the contracting party (employer), ensuring favorable working conditions and fair remuneration in compliance with current legislation.

However, despite the protective principle of Labor Law, Brazil is experiencing a period of precarious employment, disguised as modernity, where the State, which once granted numerous rights, is now gradually withdrawing them, justifying this by claiming that innovations in the field and the streamlining of labor laws are necessary to resume economic growth and the creation of new jobs, hence ensuring competitiveness in the market.

The world is constantly changing. Thence, it is only natural that the norms governing interpersonal relationships, including in the workplace, are modified over time to adapt to social dynamics. Nevertheless, the erosion of social rights and the precariousness of labor relations must be prevented, preserving the right to decent work.

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